

Finding Hope and Resilience: A Child Courageous Battle Journey with Myasthenia Gravis in Crisis

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Abstract:

A very rare autoimmune condition of the peripheral nervous system is named as myasthenia gravis it enables antibodies to be created against acetylcholine nicotinic postsynaptic receptors at the myoneuronal junction. Case report: Here, we discussed the admission of a 2-year-old child to the paediatric critical care unit as a result of a myasthenia gravis in crisis. The child's symptoms were limited facial movements, ptosis, and trouble in chewing. Weakening of the oropharyngeal/respiratory muscles, exhaustion, and recurrent respiratory infection. A few testing were carried out on him, including the edrophonium-tensilon test, blood analysis (Hb), ACHR

antibodies, and imaging examinations (CT, MRI, X-ray). Genetic analysis Sample: to NIMHANS Bangalore, India. Efficient execution of treatment purposes, both corticosteroids and cholinesterase inhibitors. The NG tube has been placed, the child is on Nil Per oral (NPO) until he recovers. If properly managed, contemporaneous medical issues have minimal effect on the underlying conditions.

Keywords: *myasthenia gravis, child, autoimmune disorder, myasthenia crisis, cholinesterase inhibitors.*

Introduction

An autoimmune disease referred to as myasthenia gravis (MG) is characterized by antibodies that destroy the acetylcholine receptors at the postsynaptic membrane of the neuromuscular junction. This results in variable degrees of muscle weakening and fatigability. Childhood variations of MG can appear as congenital, juvenile, or transitory. According to recent studies, up to 29% of all instances of MG occur in youngsters. Since MG is uncommon in children and can present with symptoms like limb weakness, ptosis, and bulbar involvement that can be confused with organophosphate

poisoning, snake bites, botulism, and diphtheritic polyneuropathy, it is often misdiagnosed in the first year of the illness. Up to one-fifth of MG cases may begin with a myasthenia crisis; however, barring that could be fatal if not identified and treated right away.

It often manifests as a neuromuscular junction dysfunction, which can be hereditary or acquired. The proximal, bulbar, or extra ocular muscles are typically affected by these pure motor disorders. The development of myasthenia gravis occurs in infancy or adolescence in about 20% of cases. The characteristic is fatigable frailty. Ptosis or

ophthalmoplegia affect the majority of the patients. It could change over time and be asymmetrical. Pupillary reactions are typical. Children may have diplopia, particularly while staring straight ahead or when reading while trying to tightly cover their eyes. After a short while, this condition can cause the cornea to become exposed because the orbicularis oculi cannot constrict for a prolonged period of time. We introduce a young person in this instance whose recognition of such a crisis and prompt therapeutic beginning gave a favourable result.

Brief Report

A 2-year-old male presented to the PICU services, with complaints of multiple episodes of difficulty in swallowing food for 2–3-days. He also complained of difficulty in getting up from the floor, running, going up stairs, and lifting her arms above her head. The difficulty in swallowing also worsened in the evening. He had history of diurnal variation was present. The child also experienced common cold and fever for 2 days. The child also experienced difficulty in opening her eyes completely more in the evening and complained of blurring of vision worsening at night and improving after some rest. The child also experienced respiratory distress during admission time due to that oxygen therapy is administrated. The child complains about vomiting episodes. The child did not complain of any fever, muscle pains, tenderness, rash, or joint pains. There was no prior history of any animal bite, presence of snakes in the neighbourhood, neck swelling, drug intake, pesticide exposure, recent vaccination, recent canned food intake, diarrhoea/vomiting preceding weakness, poisoning, or any abnormal body movements.

The child had been born at term, the first-born of a non-consanguineous marriage, with an uneventful antenatal, natal, and postnatal period. He was completely immunized as per the national immunization schedule, and he had achieved all her developmental milestones appropriately for age. There was no significant medical illness in the family. On examination, the child was conscious, alert, and afebrile with

a heart rate of 116b/min, respiratory rate 26/min, and blood pressure 90/60 mmHg. His weight was 8.7 kg (between 25th and 50th centile), height was 82.5 cm (between 3rd centile), and mid arm circumference was 12.5 cm, the degree of malnutrition is 72.5%. There was no pallor, cyanosis, icterus, clubbing, lymphadenopathy, or edema. There were no signs of Vitamin B/C/D deficiency. Neurological examination revealed bilateral ptosis with a slightly decreased range of eye movements, especially while looking upward and in lateral gaze, normal pupillary size, and reaction. There was a weak gag reflex, dysphonia, and drooling of saliva. Motor system evaluation revealed decreased muscle power in all limbs (proximal > distal) with normal deep tendon reflexes and flexor plantar response. Fundoscopic examination, sensory system, and cerebellar examination were unremarkable. On auscultation of the chest, there were no murmurs or abnormal heart sounds. Normal vesicular breath sounds were heard in all lung fields and there were no adventitious sounds. Abdominal examination was also unremarkable with no organomegaly and normal bowel sounds on auscultation. He underwent even edrophonium test and tensilon test.

He underwent few investigations such as Hb 73 gm/dl, Platelet count is 502 ul, CPK 79 IU/L, Acetyl choline Receptor binding antibody 1.87 mmol/l, and then he underwent some special investigations like Chest X- ray, CT Brain done for him and Genetic analysis Sample: to NIMHANS Bangalore, India.

Efficient execution of treatment purposes, both corticosteroids and cholinesterase inhibitors were used to treat the boy. His respiratory infection resolved up. The NG tube has been placed, during the hospital stay the child is on Nil Per oral (NPO) until he recovers and vital indicators were closely monitored.

Oral pyridostigmine (7 mg/kg/day in 4 divided doses) and supportive care were initiated for the youngster. Over the course of the following 12 hours, he became better; his ptosis and muscle weakness subsided; and additional tests, such as a computed tomography of the chest, did not

show any thymic growth. The amount of antineutrophil antibodies in serum was normal. 1.87 mmol/L of serum acetylcholine receptor antibodies was measured (normal < 0.4 nmol/L). For the next two weeks, oral pyridostigmine (7 mg/kg/day in four separate doses) was continued and gradually decreased.

A final diagnosis of juvenile MG in crisis (JMG) was made after careful consideration of the results of the clinical and laboratory examinations. The illness's severity was classified as Class V MG Foundation of America. After three weeks, the child's symptoms improved, and at three months, they continued to do so.

The child became symptomatically better over the next 3 weeks and at 3-month follow-up, the youngster continued to be healthy, showing no signs of neurological weakness and only sporadic instances of ptosis and weakening fluctuations. Parents were counsel regarding what to do in the event of another crisis. In the interim, whole exome sequencing's mutation screening for congenital MG genes produced a negative result, ruling out the possibility of a congenital MG variant diagnosis.

Results

The most common type of young children MG is juvenile MG. While the clinical characteristics of juvenile MG share many similarities with MG with an adult start, the presentation of JMG in children is typically more severe. Nearly 65% of patients have ptosis, while older children typically complain of diplopia. Additionally, 25% of patients have dysphagia and facial paralysis. Weakness and exhaustion in the extremities are typical. Youngsters who first only exhibit ocular symptoms may go on to develop generalized JMG. As demonstrated by our patient, many youngsters can initially appear with bulbar symptoms and respiratory weakness associated with myasthenic crises.

Discussion

Antibodies against the AChR are the primary diagnostic tool for juvenile myopathy (MG),

supporting the clinical diagnosis. It is uncommon for youngsters to have muscle-specific kinase antibody (Anti MuSK) positive MG. Due to economical limitations, anti-MuSK antibodies could not be projected for our patient. Congenital forms of MG have a genetic basis, appear earlier in childhood or infancy, and have a more stable course than JMG, which is an autoimmune condition with characteristic symptom swings that typically appear in puberty. In our situation, genetic study ruled out congenital MG.

The distinctive decremental responses in muscle action potentials following repetitive nerve stimulation are demonstrated by electrophysiology tests such as the repetitive nerve stimulation test (RNST). But, we were unable to do the same for our child because of technical issues with young children, particularly with the ocular muscles, and financial constraints. Further, a negative RNST does not rule out JMG; rather, it may indicate the need for additional testing or for other neuromuscular illnesses to be further evaluated. As such, MG is still primarily diagnosed clinically. To aid in the diagnostic process, a few clinical tests can be used, such as the ice pack test, the repeated opening and closing of the hands, and the fatigability in prolonged upgaze.

The diagnosis in our instance was validated by a positive anti-AChR test and a positive neostigmine challenge test. In 9.4% of children with JMG, autoimmune diseases like thyroid disease, rheumatoid arthritis, and juvenile onset diabetes mellitus may manifest. Furthermore, as it is thought to be the location where these antibodies are created, imaging for thymoma or thymic dysplasia is suggested. An imminent myasthenic crisis requires hospitalization in critical care along with close observation of bulbar and respiratory function. Acetylcholinesterase inhibitors, such as pyridostigmine and neostigmine, are used as first-line therapy to relieve symptoms. For a quick cure, intravenous immunoglobulin and plasma exchange are utilized to quickly lower the levels of pathogenic antibodies.

Acetylcholine levels are raised by the cholinesterase inhibitor pyridostigmine, which momentarily enhances muscle strength. Corticosteroids or other immunosuppressive drugs are started for the long term. Compared to children with post pubertal onset of disease, children in pre pubertal years are more likely to experience complete stable remission, which is defined as being off therapy for at least a year without experiencing any signs or symptoms of MG.

Conclusion

Although juvenile MG is a rare disorder in children, it should be taken into consideration whenever a child exhibits erratic weakness and fatigue. A youngster with neurological weakness that rapidly worsens to involve respiratory and bulbar muscles may be suspected of having a myasthenic crisis. A high level of suspicion combined with prompt, appropriate treatment can save lives. Learnings Patients with generalized muscle weakness may be evaluated for rare disorders like juvenile myasthenia gravis (JMG) once more prevalent conditions have been ruled out. If symptoms suddenly worsen and involve the bulbar region, there is a strong suspicion that myasthenic crisis is to blame. A successful outcome may result from early detection of a life-threatening myasthenic crisis, prompt therapeutic beginning, and early diagnosis of JMG.

Recommendation

The inspiring story of a child's courageous battle with Myasthenia Gravis, highlighting the importance of hope and resilience in the face of adversity. We aim to educate healthcare providers and families about the complexities of MG crisis and the vital role of interdisciplinary care. The significance of family support, community engagement, and adaptive coping strategies in promoting hope and resilience. It provides a unique perspective on the human experience of living with MG, offering valuable insights for healthcare providers and families.

By sharing this condition, we hope to inspire and resilience in other child facing similar challenges; this emphasize the importance of interdisciplinary care and family support in managing MG crisis and to highlight coping mechanisms and strategies employed by the child and family to promote hope and resilience.

Acknowledgment

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Declaration of Interest

The authors affirm that they have all relevant patient authorization information in their possession. The legal guardian agreed in writing for the clinical data to be published in the journal. The guardian is aware that while every attempt will be made to hide the identity and that names and initials will not be published, anonymity cannot be ensured.

Author Contribution

Mrs. R. Nithyapriya - Conceptualization of the study, formulation of report, and information.

Mrs. B. Ramya - Data collection, coordination with child & family members, and administration of the knowledge regarding assessment & care.

Mrs. R. Nithyapriya - Writing of the manuscript draft, literature review, and manuscript editing.

Mrs. B. Ramya - Final review of the manuscript, approval of the final version for submission, and supervision of the overall project.

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No funding was provided for this investigation.

Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests regarding the study "Finding Hope and Resilience: A Child's Courageous Battle Journey with Myasthenia Gravis in Crisis." The report was taken with the sole intention of sharing insights into the challenges and resilience displayed by a child facing myasthenia gravis. The authors have no financial, personal, or professional conflicts that could have influenced the research, interpretation, or presentation of the case. Additionally, no external organizations or entities had any involvement in the funding, design, or execution of the study.

Ethical Clearance

Every procedure in this investigation complied with equivalent ethical standards or the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its revisions. "The ethical aspect of the study has been institutionally reviewed". Informed consent has been procured by all respondents in this study.

The legal guardian agreed in writing for the clinical data to be published in the journal. The guardian is aware that while every attempt will be made to hide the identity. I want to acknowledge the child parents and my teachers for supporting me to undertake the case to deliver nursing care.

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